

Table 1: Medical claim extraction prompt example.

System Message:

You are an expert in the medical domain.

User Message:

–Goal–

Extract and analyze all relevant medical entities from the text and map the relationships among them, ensuring accurate representation.

–Steps–

1. **Entity Identification:** Extract each medical entity with the following details:

- **entity_name:** Name of the entity, always capitalized.
- **entity_type:** Category of the entity (e.g., Disease, Symptom, Drug).
- **entity_description:** A detailed description including attributes and functions.

2. **Relationship Identification:** Identify all relevant pairs of related entities and classify the relationship type based on predefined categories.

- **Types of Relationships:** ['exposure_exposure', 'protein_protein', 'pathway_protein', 'anatomy_protein_absent', 'anatomy_protein_present', 'cellcomp_protein', 'off-label use', 'cellcomp_cellcomp', 'exposure_molfunc', 'pathway_pathway', 'exposure_bioprocess', 'phenotype_protein', 'exposure_cellcomp', 'contraindication', 'exposure_protein', 'drug_effect', 'indication', 'molfunc_molfunc', 'disease_disease', 'exposure_disease', 'drug_drug', 'disease_protein', 'molfunc_protein', 'bioprocess_protein', 'disease_phenotype_negative', 'bioprocess_bioprocess', 'anatomy_anatomy', 'phenotype_phenotype', 'disease_phenotype_positive', 'drug_protein'].

3. **Relationship Validation:** Remove redundant relationships where two terms refer to the same conceptual entity to prevent overlapping or duplicate relationships.

4. **Output Generation:** Compile all validated and scored relationships into a list, formatted as:

(<source_entity >{tuple_delimiter} <target_entity>{tuple_delimiter} <relationship_description>).

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–Examples–

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Example 1:

Text: The patient's symptoms of poor urine flow and taking a long time to empty the bladder suggest a urethral obstruction, which is most likely due to a urethral stricture. The patient's previous episode of non-gonococcal urethritis may have caused scarring or inflammation leading to a stricture.

Output:

(Non-gonococcal urethritis{tuple_delimiter}Urethral stricture{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)
 (Urethral obstruction{tuple_delimiter}Poor urine flow{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)
 (Urethral obstruction{tuple_delimiter}Long time to empty{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)
 (Urethral stricture{tuple_delimiter}Urethral obstruction{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)
 (Non-gonococcal urethritis{tuple_delimiter}Scarring{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)
 (Non-gonococcal urethritis{tuple_delimiter}Inflammation{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)

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Example 2:

Text: The case description seems to be of migraine with a surprisingly abrupt onset of headache. It is the abrupt onset of headache is the most worrying feature and suggests a serious underlying cause. Abrupt onset of headache with visual disturbance could be due to subarachnoid haemorrhage (possibly a haemorrhage into the occipital lobe, e.g. from an intracerebral arteriovenous malformation), or haemorrhage into a pituitary macroadenoma with compression of the anterior visual pathway. Other possibilities include reversible cerebral vasoconstriction syndrome, cerebral venous sinus thrombosis or low-pressure headache, though visual disturbance would not be easily explained.

Output:

(Migraine{tuple_delimiter}Abrupt onset of headache{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)
 (Abrupt onset of headache{tuple_delimiter}Subarachnoid haemorrhage{tuple_delimiter}exposure_disease)
 (Visual disturbance{tuple_delimiter}Subarachnoid haemorrhage{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)
 (Intracerebral arteriovenous malformation{tuple_delimiter}Subarachnoid haemorrhage{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)
 (Pituitary macroadenoma{tuple_delimiter}Subarachnoid haemorrhage{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)

Continued on next page

Table 1 continued from previous page

User Message:

(Pituitary macroadenoma{tuple_delimiter}Reversible cerebral vasoconstriction syndrome{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)
(Pituitary macroadenoma{tuple_delimiter}Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)
(Pituitary macroadenoma{tuple_delimiter}Low-pressure headache{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)

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Example 3:

Text: The patient's presentation suggests tumor lysis syndrome (TLS), a common and serious complication of chemotherapy in patients with high-turnover cancers like Burkitt's lymphoma. TLS is characterized by rapid release of intracellular contents from dying tumor cells into the bloodstream, leading to metabolic abnormalities such as hyperkalemia, hyperphosphatemia, hyperuricemia, and acute kidney injury, which are reflected in her lab values (elevated potassium, creatinine, and urea). Measurement of serum urate levels, which are typically elevated in TLS due to the breakdown of purine nucleic acids, can help confirm this diagnosis and facilitate appropriate management.

Output:

(Burkitt's lymphoma{tuple_delimiter}Tumor lysis syndrome{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)
(Tumor lysis syndrome{tuple_delimiter}Metabolic abnormalities{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)
(Tumor lysis syndrome{tuple_delimiter}Hyperkalemia{tuple_delimiter}disease_symptom)
(Tumor lysis syndrome{tuple_delimiter}Hyperphosphatemia{tuple_delimiter}disease_symptom)
(Tumor lysis syndrome{tuple_delimiter}Hyperuricemia{tuple_delimiter}disease_symptom)
(Tumor lysis syndrome{tuple_delimiter}Acute kidney injury{tuple_delimiter}disease_symptom)
(Serum urate level{tuple_delimiter}Breakdown of purine nucleic acids{tuple_delimiter}phenotype_phenotype)
(Serum urate level{tuple_delimiter}Tumor lysis syndrome{tuple_delimiter}indication)

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–Real Data–

Text: . . .

Output:

Continue Prompt:

MANY entities and relationships were missed in the last extraction. Remember to ONLY emit entities that related to medicine. Add them below using the same format.

Loop Prompt:

It appears some entities and relationships may have still been missed. Answer YES — NO if there are still entities or relationships that need to be added.
